

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC

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PROJECT: EOSC Beyond, Advancing innovation and collaboration for research

PROJECT WEB SITE: <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu>

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SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief enables EU-funded projects contributing to the advancement of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to report on progress and provide input for further policy analysis and development by the European Commission. This policy brief should be understood as complementary to the other mandatory reporting materials.

Policy background:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the [European Research Area](#) (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the [ERA policy agenda](#) (in particular ERA action 1 & 8). EOSC is also recognised in the [European strategy for data](#) as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

Overall progress is steered by the EOSC tripartite governance involving the Union represented by the European Commission, the participating countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the research community represented by the EOSC Association. The second phase of development of EOSC (2021-2030) takes place in the context of the EOSC European co-programmed Partnership, which brings together the European Commission and the EOSC Association.

The [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA) co-developed with the entire EOSC community sets 3 General Objectives (GO), 14 Operational Objectives (OO) and 14 Action Areas (AA).

General Objectives (GO):

1. Open science becomes the ‘new normal’, by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.
2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.
3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

Operational Objectives (OO):

1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;
2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);
3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;
4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;
5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated

processing); 6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership; 7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025; 8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership. 9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership. 10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024; 11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025; 12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025; 13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users; 14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023.	
<u>Action Areas (AA) of a technical nature:</u> 1. Identifiers 2. Metadata and ontologies 3. FAIR metrics and certification 4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure 5. User environments 6. Resource provider environments 7. EOSC Interoperability Framework	<u>Action Areas (AA) related to boundary conditions:</u> 8. Rules of Participation 9. Landscape monitoring 10. Business models 11. Skills and training 12. Rewards and recognition 13. Communication 14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global

More information can be found from:

- https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud>
- <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about>

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (MAX 6P)

A. Overview of contributions in relation to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives

Connection to General Objectives (GO)

GO1. Open science becomes the ‘new normal’, by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.

EOSC Beyond contributes to making Open Science the new normal by developing **federated EOSC Core capabilities that support the seamless discovery, access, and composition of Open Science resources**. These capabilities are not delivered as isolated tools, but as part of a coherent, distributed infrastructure that respects the autonomy of national and thematic communities. In addition, they enable their integration into a broader European framework. By adopting a federated approach, EOSC Beyond allows diverse actors—ranging from large research infrastructures to small or emerging communities—to participate in the EOSC ecosystem without sacrificing their existing governance models or technical specificities. This federated design enhances interoperability across disciplines and countries, and strengthens the inclusiveness and resilience of the European Open Science environment. Furthermore, EOSC Beyond supports the uptake of Open Science practices and skills by providing training materials, dissemination resources, and dedicated support environments. This encourages active community involvement and co-creation of services adapted to real scientific needs.

GO2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.

EOSC Beyond facilitates seamless access, reuse, and combination of research outputs by implementing and promoting Open Access and FAIR principles across all its activities. This includes the publication of data, software, services, and documentation. In addition to following the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) guidelines, the project actively contributes to the development of a semantic foundation through a Top Level Ontology that supports consistent and machine-actionable descriptions of EOSC Core resources. This work on semantics is further complemented by the creation of structured metadata profiles tailored to the EOSC guidelines. This allows providers to describe the access conditions, usage parameters, and functional scope of their services in a harmonised and interoperable way. These profiles enhance the discoverability and composability of resources within the EOSC ecosystem, while also improving the user experience across federated environments. All project outputs are openly licensed (e.g. Creative Commons), and the development process is transparent and inclusive, fostering collaboration with researchers, civil society, and technology developers interested in contributing to or building upon EOSC Beyond results.

GO3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

EOSC Beyond designs and implements a **federated architecture that enables the open sharing of scientific results while respecting the autonomy and specific needs of diverse user communities**. Rather than imposing a centralised model, the project embraces a distributed approach where national, thematic, and institutional actors can integrate their resources into EOSC and access EOSC services locally. This federated setup allows communities to maintain control over their infrastructures and policies, while benefitting from interoperability, shared standards, and cross-border collaboration. Architecture is built to scale and sustain itself over time. It supports governance models that reflect European research's distributed nature and reinforces trust among participants.

Connection to Operational Objectives (OO)

OO1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;

EOSC Beyond will deliver results gradually over its duration, with final outcomes expected by 2027. The project follows an incremental release strategy, gradually introducing new components and services that enhance and extend the Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE). The approach ensures early adoption, continuous feedback, and iterative improvement. AAI, Accounting, Monitoring and Helpdesk are among the EOSC Core services Pilot Nodes are adopting and expressing requirements for their development. In the next generation of EOSC Core services, advanced capabilities and domain-specific user environments will go beyond the MVE and enable widespread adoption by public and private stakeholders.

OO2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023).

EOSC Beyond develops the **EOSC Monitoring system for availability and reliability of services**. Its progressive development is underway, with a first functional release scheduled for August 2025. This initial version will improve integration with the Resource Registry, enabling monitoring data to be made available through the Providers Portal. Subsequent iterations will expand its capabilities, including the automation of processes for defining and updating metrics. This will support service providers in tracking and improving their alignment with Open Science best practices.

OO3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership.

EOSC Beyond promotes and delivers **training on the EOSC Core services, new services, functionalities, and tools**. Also proactively reaches out to lead users, support user communities and coordinate internal feedback loops. This supports the co-design and initial integration of EOSC Pilot Nodes.

OO4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership.

Throughout the project's life cycle, EOSC Beyond supports the co-development of domain-specific standards and Open Science practices through close engagement with research communities. Scientific domain standards are progressively integrated through the real-life implementation of **Pilot Nodes**, which actively work towards aligning and making their standards interoperable with those supported by EOSC Core

services. To enable **cross-domain interoperability**, the project also provides **adapters** that bridge domain-specific data models and metadata schemas with the common standards adopted by the Core. These adapters facilitate seamless integration across heterogeneous scientific disciplines. By focusing on open standards adoption, avoiding vendor lock-in, and providing high-quality documentation, EOSC Core services ensure sustainable and extensible growth. In order to support collaborative and transparent development, the project uses Agile methodologies and tools such as Jira and Confluence. Software development is carried out on open platforms like GitHub, promoting community collaboration and reuse. EOSC Core services are designed, implemented, and maintained by an open-source community of developers, users, and operators—including the early integration of EOSC Pilot Nodes, which play a key role in validating and guiding interoperability solutions.

OO5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)

Although EOSC Beyond started in 2024, after the original 2023 target of this objective, it actively contributes to this objective. This is done by **progressively delivering technical components that support the FAIR ecosystem**. These include open specifications, APIs, metadata schemas, and validation frameworks designed to enable the description, exchange, and automated processing of FAIR digital objects. All developments are aligned with community standards and released incrementally, allowing early feedback and iterative improvement. This ensures that the outputs are not only technically robust, but also adaptable and ready for uptake and customisation by diverse research communities across EOSC.

OO6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership.

EOSC Beyond is not directly related to this objective. However, **EOSC Core and community services are FAIR by design from an architectural and implementation point of view**, and the project gathers indicators that could be used to measure the adoption of FAIR principles, like the #Contributors in the EOSC open-source community or the # Internal/External communities contributing to co-design.

OO7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025.

EOSC Beyond is not directly related to this objective. However, **all software developed within the project is open-source and open to the research community and shared in community catalogues**. Also, Software Quality Assurance as a Service checks the quality of the code shared in the EOSC Sandbox.

OO8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership.

EOSC Beyond is not directly addressing this objective, as the project does not include a dedicated activity for developing a formal Rewards and Recognition framework. However, **FAIR and open data practices are followed and encouraged** throughout the project. In particular, EOSC Beyond supports the adoption of **common metadata profiles** that include key elements such as **DOIs, licences, and provenance information**, which contribute to the traceability and citability of resources. These profiles are progressively implemented in the EOSC Core service descriptions and provider registries, laying the foundation for future recognition mechanisms based on openness and reusability.

OO9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership.

While EOSC Beyond is not directly related to this objective, the Rules of Participation and the onboarding process directly affect how services created by this project and those offered by the EOSC Pilot Nodes can be onboarded. As mentioned in AA6, the [EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox](#) will increase operational readiness and contribute to the EOSC Federation. In addition, EOSC Beyond's contributions to the [EOSC Federation Handbook](#) and the [EOSC Federation: Architecture and Federating Capabilities concept paper](#) contribute to the definition of an evolving EOSC Federation, and how its participants will collaborate.

OO10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024.

EOSC Beyond began in 2024 and **enhances the EOSC Core AAI and the EOSC AAI Federation**. This is done by further enhancing AAI interoperability between the EOSC AAI Federation members. In particular, the project works on an OIDC-based model for AAI Federation.

OO11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025.

EOSC Beyond began in 2024, and develops a **PIDs service for the assignment and resolution of PIDs to**

providers and resources onboarded into the EOSC Service Catalogue.
OO12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025
EOSC Beyond, which started in 2024, addresses OO12 through a set of concrete actions. As part of this effort, the project has produced the EOSC Federation: Architecture and Federating Capabilities concept paper , which outlines the foundational design for how nodes in the federation interoperate — including how metadata is exchanged, harmonised, and made discoverable across the federation. This concept paper provides the architectural vision and technical guidelines for enabling a common search and access mechanism , by defining the role of shared capabilities such as metadata harvesting, indexing, and service integration. Building on this, EOSC Beyond is also delivering a Metadata Aggregator Service , designed to collect and harmonise structured metadata across nodes, based on the Interoperability Framework Guidelines , which include domain-aligned and extensible metadata profiles. In parallel, the project is developing practical tools for federated discovery and access , enabling users to search and access EOSC resources across distributed nodes through a unified interface, fully aligned with the minimum metadata framework envisioned in this objective.
OO13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users.
The uptake of the EOSC Core services developed by the project and of the EOSC Exchange resources provided by the EOSC Pilot Nodes is continuously monitored with appropriate KPIs reported to the EC in periodic reports and deliverables. Additionally, we ensure there is a feedback loop with the users , as described in the response to OO3.
OO14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023.
EOSC Beyond began in 2024 and develops EOSC Core components related to Monitoring , which provides information on service availability. It also provides Accounting and Credit Management , which will facilitate calculating service costing.

Connection to Activity Areas (AA)
AA1. Identifiers
EOSC Beyond provides new capabilities to manage PIDs in EOSC . These capabilities include resolution, minting and interlinking of PIDs for service instances describing identical services onboarded from different EOSC Nodes, accounting for PIDs, and creating machine-readable type descriptions for supported resources.
AA2. Metadata ontologies
EOSC Beyond evolves the structured metadata profiles to represent EOSC resources (e.g. services, datasets, Nodes) enabling machine actionable access to them.
AA3. FAIR metrics and certification
This area is not addressed in the project.
AA4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure
EOSC Beyond will support OpenID Connect Federations enabling connecting to the EOSC AAI Federation without the need for a SAML to OpenID Connect/OAuth 2.0 proxy layer. Multifactor Authentication (MFA) and advanced authorisation mechanisms will also be supported. It will also offer interoperability with SIMPL middleware .
AA5. User environments
With EOSC Beyond's Execution Framework and Discovery Hub , users can discover and create reproducible computational environments, as well as increase science reproducibility.
AA6. Resource provider environments
EOSC Beyond develops the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox as a testing environment for the production of the EOSC Federation that will facilitate prototyping enhanced and new EOSC Core services, and allow providers to validate their integration with the EOSC before deploying services into production as third party services or as Nodes.
AA7. EOSC Interoperability Framework
EOSC Beyond is developing an enhanced Interoperability Framework Registry which allows for machine-composable resources. The IF Registry will take care of setting up IF Guidelines configurations, which are structured metadata profiles that allow providers to describe actual access parameters of their services.
AA8. Rules of Participation

The EOSC Beyond provides feedback and keeps informed about the Rules of Participation's implementation. Also, provides input to their definition with the actions mentioned in OO9.
AA9. Landscape monitoring
There is no scope for this area in the project.
AA10. Business models
The project studies financial sustainability for the next generation of EOSC Core and horizontal services by analysing options and opportunities for future exploitation. It will publish its initial analysis and recommendations in D3.3 in September 2025.
AA11. Skills and training
The delivery of training on the EOSC Core services, new services, functionalities, and tools is part of the Service Promotion, user community support and coordination task. One result is a series of eBooks and slide decks that inform users about three Core services that are being developed: the EOSC Innovation Sandbox, the EOSC Execution Framework, and the EOSC Integration Suite.
AA12. Rewards and recognition
FAIR and open data practices are followed and encouraged.
AA13. Communication
EOSC Beyond implements communication activities, like news , to inform target groups about the project's achievements, and coordinate events and activities . EOSC Beyond aligns with the overall EOSC guidelines and participates in meetings and activities with other EOSC-related projects , increasing awareness of the EOSC brand and EOSC Core services.
AA14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global Business models
As part of the project, beneficiaries engage with the public sector , and the EOSC Digital Innovation Hub (EOSC DIH) supports exploitation through the private sector.

B. Key contributions subject to wider dissemination by the European Commission

In terms of dissemination, the following were the main contributions by EOSC Beyond during the first half of the project that could be disseminated by the EC:

- Publication: the concept paper [“EOSC Federation: Architecture and Federating Capabilities”](#) - published in October 2024 - contributed to GO3, attracting more than 1700 downloads on Zenodo and impacting subsequent development of the EOSC Federation Handbook.
- Service: The [EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox](#) is officially open to a first set of external users who wish to test and integrate their solutions with EOSC. There is a dedicated contact form on the [website](#) to learn more.
- Skills/Training: A first set of [EOSC Beyond dissemination resources](#) was published in March 2025, including slides and factsheets introducing the new services currently developed in the project.

C. Synergies with other stakeholders

Collaboration with EOSC Association

EOSC Beyond representatives routinely participate in the three collaboration groups on technology, communication, and impact, facilitated by the EOSC Focus project (followed up by EOSC Gravity in June 2025), as well as in key invitation-only meetings, such as the EOSC Winter School and the Annual coordination meetings of EOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe, organised by the European Commission in June 2024 and 2025. In addition, input was provided by EOSC Beyond project representatives to the writing of the EOSC Federation Handbook, which drew on the knowledge and experience of EOSC Beyond and helped ensure the Handbook reflected the latest considerations relating to EOSC Nodes and their federation.

Collaboration with EOSC Projects

Results from the EOSC Projects have been used to develop the EOSC Core and horizontal services of the Exchange, including EOSC Future, EGI-ACE, OpenAIRE Nexus, DICE, EOSC Enhance, and EOSC-hub. EOSC Beyond collaborated with EOSC Focus on the analysis of project results and alignment with the EOSC Landscape. This contributed to the **EOSC Macro Roadmap**. EOSC Beyond invited several projects such as OSCARS and FAIRCORE4EOSC to its first Pilot Node workshop in June 2024. It has also jointly organised a workshop with FAIRCORE4EOSC at the EUDAT Conference 2024 to introduce the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. Furthermore, EOSC Beyond closely collaborates with EOSC Procurement contractors

related to the EOSC EU Node. It pays particular attention to the implementation of the EOSC Rules of Participation during the service onboarding process. Liaison is also established with Smart Middleware Platform Operators. A range of projects such as AquaINFRA are currently in touch to explore possibilities in the Sandbox.

Collaboration with other EU-Funded projects

The main collaboration with a non-EOSC project has been established through the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with **EUreka3D** and its successor **EUreka3D-XR**. This agreement lays the groundwork for a long-term collaboration aimed at amplifying digital solutions for cultural heritage within the EOSC ecosystem. The partnership is expected to enhance **technical interoperability**, **foster data sharing**, and **enable knowledge exchange** between the involved communities. In addition to this, EOSC Beyond is currently in discussion with the **ENVRI-Hub NEXT** project to explore the evolution of ENVRI-Hub and its potential alignment with the emerging EOSC architecture. These conversations aim to ensure that environmental research infrastructures can be effectively integrated into the federated EOSC landscape. Furthermore, EOSC Beyond has initiated contact with the **European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS)**, with the shared intention of formalising collaboration through a dedicated MoU. This prospective agreement would support the integration of heritage science services and datasets into EOSC. It would also contribute to the wider adoption of FAIR principles across the cultural heritage domain.

Collaboration with other stakeholders

EOSC Beyond has initiated coordination meetings with the **SIMPL project**, with the shared goal of technical interoperability between EOSC and SIMPL. A dedicated technical roadmap has been defined to guide this process, ensuring compatibility across platforms and enabling the seamless exchange of services and data. In parallel, EOSC Beyond collaborates with initiatives linked to the **EU Data Spaces**. Integration plans have been outlined and several **co-design workshops** have already taken place. Preliminary **node interaction maps** have been developed to visualise and optimise the connections between EOSC Nodes and various Data Space environments. These efforts aim to ensure that EOSC is effectively positioned as a federated layer across multiple sectors. This will enable robust and scalable data sharing across both public and private domains.

D. EOSC challenges and lessons learnt of a policy nature

From a technical perspective, one of the key challenges encountered by EOSC Beyond is the **harmonisation of diverse architectural frameworks** across EOSC Nodes and related platforms. Ensuring interoperability in a federated environment—where autonomy, heterogeneity, and scalability must coexist—requires the careful alignment of specifications, governance rules, and implementation timelines.

Another critical area is the **definition and enforcement of policies**, particularly regarding **data protection** and responsibility allocation in a distributed setting. To address this, EOSC Beyond is developing a **Data Protection Management System (DPMS)** designed to support providers in defining, implementing, and documenting compliance measures aligned with GDPR and other regulatory frameworks. This effort reinforces trust and transparency in the EOSC ecosystem, especially in contexts where sensitive or regulated data is involved.

Further complexity has emerged around the **EOSC Innovation Sandbox**, which functions as a container for deploying and testing services. Rather than centralising governance, the Sandbox delegated **policy definition and operational control** to individual Nodes or service providers contributing to the environment. This design choice respects the federated nature of EOSC. However, it also highlights the need for **clear policy interfaces and coordination mechanisms** to ensure consistency, security, and legal accountability across services.

The project also faced **coordination challenges** related to synchronising development cycles among distributed teams and third-party contributors. These have been partially mitigated by adopting **Agile methodologies** and using tools such as **Jira** and **Confluence**. This enables iterative delivery and responsive planning across work packages.

Policy recommendation: To support sustainable technical development and service onboarding within EOSC, it is essential to establish **shared policy frameworks**—especially for data protection, security, and liability—complemented by **interoperability guidelines** co-designed with stakeholders from EOSC and

adjacent ecosystems (e.g., Data Spaces, SIMPL). Moreover, the introduction of a **lightweight but coordinated technical governance model** would ensure long-term compatibility and mutual recognition of policies and standards.

E. Link to other EU policy priorities (beyond EOSC)

EOSC Beyond Destination ‘Enabling an operational, open, and FAIR EOSC ecosystem (INFRAEOSC)’ contributes to the development of an infrastructure that supports research in scientific and technical areas related to accomplishing all five [EU Missions in Horizon Europe](#).

In terms of the EU Sectoral Policy domains and the EU Policy for Open Science, EOSC Beyond contributes to Research and Innovation. This is done by advocating in pursuit of the adoption of Open Science practices and technologies to support open research infrastructures. Also, EOSC Beyond contributes to the [European Data Strategy](#), as the project supports the seamless access and reliable re-use of research data to European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens through a trusted and open distributed data environment and related interoperable services that are developed within the project activities. In addition, EOSC Beyond collaborates with the EU Data Spaces (in particular developing a proof of concept with SIMPL) in supporting FAIR for interoperability.

EOSC Beyond also actively contributes to UNESCO's recommendations on Open Science, by creating open, inclusive, and transparent Open Science infrastructure and services to increase scientific collaboration, supporting information sharing for science and society, and strengthening international cooperation on Open Science.

EOSC Beyond does not focus on Sustainable Development Goals, however, we consider it has an impact on SDG8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, SDG5 Gender equality, SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, and SDG17 International cooperation through the work developed. Also, EGI participated in the 79th Session of the UN General Assembly (UNGA 79) Science Summit in September 2024 and presented the project as a beneficiary fulfilling its obligation to maximise impact. EGI presented the project objectives and activities, and emphasised how these and the EOSC nodes piloted, like the Lifewatch ERIC thematic Pilot Node, could support the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals as part of the session ‘Transforming Knowledge into Practice: Science, Technology and Innovation in Support of the UN SDGs’. The session abstract is available here: [‘Transforming Knowledge into Practice: Science, Technology and Innovation in Support of the UN SDGs’](#).

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY (MAX 1P)

EOSC Beyond will fill-in this section in the final reporting period.